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Influence of nacelle-lidar scanning patterns on inflow turbulence characterization

Wei Fu, Alessandro Sebastiani, Alfredo Peña, Jakob Mann

Department of Wind Energy, Technical University of Denmark, Frederiksborgvej 399, 4000 Roskilde, Denmark

E-mail: weif@dtu.dk

Abstract. Nacelle lidars with different number of beams, scanning configurations and focus distances are simulated for characterizing the inflow turbulence. Lidar measurements are simulated within 100 turbulence wind fields described by the Mann model. The reference wind turbine has a rotor diameter of 52 m. We assume homogeneous frozen turbulence over the lidar scanning area. The lidar-derived Reynolds stresses are computed from a least-square procedure that uses radial velocity variances of each of the beams and compared with those from a simulated sonic anemometer at turbine hub height. Results show that at least six beams, including one beam with a different opening angle, are needed to estimate all Reynolds stresses. Enlarging the beam opening angle improves the accuracy and uncertainty in turbulence estimation more than increasing the number of beams. All simulated lidars can estimate the along-wind variance accurately. This work provides guidance on designing and utilizing nacelle lidars for inflow turbulence characterization.

1. Introduction

Characteristics of inflow turbulence are crucial for wind turbine load validation [1], power performance assessment [2] and wind turbine control [3]. In-situ anemometers installed on meteorological masts, such as cup and sonic anemometers, have been used to measure inflow turbulence. Nevertheless, with the increasing size of modern wind turbines, installing a meteorological mast that reaches the height of the blade tips has becoming more and more unaffordable, especially in offshore conditions. In recent years, lidars of different types and configurations have been mounted on the nacelle of wind turbines to scan the inflow [2; 4]. These forward-looking nacelle lidars have the advantage that they yaw with the wind turbine and scan towards the main wind direction. Compared to the point-wise anemometers, lidars measure over an area in front of the rotor, which gives the possibility to derive rotor-averaged turbulence characteristics.

Turbulence can be characterized by the second-order moments (variances and covariances) of the wind field components u, v and w in typically 10 min or 30 min assuming statistical stationarity. A matrix containing these six second-order moments $\langle u'_i u'_j \rangle$ is known as the Reynolds stress tensor, which is frequently used to describe atmospheric flow. The along-wind variance is widely used in wind energy as it is part of the definition of the turbulence intensity, which is an important turbulence parameter for turbine structural loads [5]. The momentum fluxes (i.e., two covariances $\langle u'w' \rangle$ and $\langle v'w' \rangle$) are used to calculate the friction velocity, which is closely connected to the vertical wind profile [6; 7]. The turbulence kinetic energy, i.e., half

the sum of the variances of the three velocity components, is a key parameter for studying wind turbine wake structure [8]. The Reynolds stresses are also useful for evaluating the three-dimensional turbulence models for e.g., load simulations.

Compared to turbulence estimates from sonic anemometers, lidar-derived turbulence characteristics can be biased due to the lidar scanning patterns, the spatial and temporal resolutions intrinsic to the lidar systems and the characteristics of atmospheric turbulence. [1; 9] studied the application of lidar measurements from different scanning patterns for load validation. [10] optimized the scanning trajectory of nacelle lidars based on a coherence model for the rotor-effective wind speed for control applications. Only a few works have investigated the influence of lidar scanning pattern on turbulence characterization. [11] proposed an optimized six-beam configuration using an objective function for a ground-based lidar to minimize the sum of the random errors of the Reynolds stresses. [12] showed that turbulence estimates from ground-based lidars can be improved by using the variance from the vertical beam.

Here, we compare the estimates of the Reynolds stress tensor from nacelle lidars with different scanning patterns through numerical simulations. The Reynolds stresses are computed via a least-square procedure that uses radial velocity variances for each of the lidars' beams without the need to reconstruct the wind components. We summarize how the number of beams, the half-cone opening angle and focus distance influence the accuracy and the uncertainty of turbulence estimates. This work provides guidance on designing and utilizing nacelle lidars for inflow turbulence characterization.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the simulated turbulence wind fields and the methodology to estimate the Reynolds stresses. Section 3 provides information on the simulated lidar scanning patterns and the simulation setup. Section 4 shows the comparison of Reynolds stress estimation between the virtual lidars and sonic anemometer. Conclusion and outlook are given in Section 5.

2. Methodology

2.1. Turbulence wind fields

Assuming homogeneous frozen turbulence [13], the wind fields can be described by a vector field $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) = (u, v, w)$, where u is the horizontal along-wind component, v the horizontal lateral component, w the vertical component, and $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z)$ the position vector defined in a right-handed coordinate system. The mean value of the homogeneous velocity field is $\langle \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) \rangle = (U, 0, 0)$, so the coordinate x is in the mean wind direction. We simulate lidar measurements on the nacelle of a wind turbine with a rotor diameter (D) of 52 m using 100 randomly generated turbulence fields described by the Mann model [14; 15]. The wind fields have typical values of the model parameters: $\alpha\varepsilon^{2/3} = 0.05 \text{ m}^{4/3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which is related to the turbulent energy dissipation rate; $L = 61 \text{ m}$, which is a turbulent length scale; and $\Gamma = 3.2$, which describes the anisotropy of the turbulence. The turbulence boxes have lengths of 30 m in the along-wind direction assuming a mean wind $U = 10 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. We add a linear shear $dU/dz = 0.0288 \text{ s}^{-1}$ to the u components in each box. The lengths are 128 m both in the vertical and lateral directions. The number of grid points in the three directions are $(N_x, N_y, N_z) = (8192, 64, 64)$. Sonic anemometer statistics are taken at the location of the turbine rotor (i.e., center of the turbulence boxes) as the reference for evaluation of the lidar-derived turbulence characteristics.

2.2. Estimation of the Reynolds stresses

The Reynolds stress tensor $R_{ij}(\mathbf{x}) \equiv \langle u'_i u'_j \rangle$, where u_i are the fluctuations around the mean, contains the variances $\sigma_{u,v,w}^2$ and the covariances of the velocity components:

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_u^2 & \langle u'v' \rangle & \langle u'w' \rangle \\ \langle v'u' \rangle & \sigma_v^2 & \langle v'w' \rangle \\ \langle w'u' \rangle & \langle w'v' \rangle & \sigma_w^2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

The unit vector \mathbf{n} describing the beam orientation of a nacelle lidar can be expressed as [4]:

$$\mathbf{n}(\phi, \theta) = (-\cos \phi, \cos \theta \sin \phi, \sin \theta \sin \phi), \quad (2)$$

where θ is the angle between the y axis and \mathbf{n} projected onto the y - z plane and ϕ is the angle between the beam and the negative x -axis (the half-cone opening angle). If we assume the lidar probe volume can be negligible and u , v , and w do not change over the scanned area, the radial velocity can be expressed as

$$v_r(\phi, \theta) = -u \cos \phi + v \cos \theta \sin \phi + w \sin \theta \sin \phi. \quad (3)$$

The radial velocity variance can be derived by taking the variance of Eq. (3), as shown in [16]:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{v_r}^2(\phi, \theta) &= \sigma_u^2 \cos^2 \phi + \sigma_v^2 \cos^2 \theta \sin^2 \phi + \sigma_w^2 \sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \phi - 2\langle u'v' \rangle \cos \phi \cos \theta \sin \phi \\ &\quad - 2\langle u'w' \rangle \cos \phi \sin \theta \sin \phi + 2\langle v'w' \rangle \sin^2 \phi \cos \theta \sin \theta. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

To compute the Reynolds stress tensor \mathbf{R} , we use the simulated lidar radial velocity variance from all beams over the scanning pattern. Assuming statistical homogeneity, we apply a least-square fit to all radial velocity variances $\sigma_{v_r}^2$ and the beam unit vectors \mathbf{n} :

$$\Delta^2 = \int (\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{R} \mathbf{n} - \sigma_{v_r}^2)^2 d\mu. \quad (5)$$

The matrix R_{ij} that minimizes the integral must fulfill

$$\frac{\partial \Delta^2}{\partial R_{ij}} = 0 \Rightarrow \int (\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{R} \mathbf{n} - \sigma_{v_r}^2) n_i n_j d\mu = 0. \quad (6)$$

This can be written as

$$R_{kl} \int n_k n_l n_i n_j d\mu = \int \sigma_{v_r}^2 n_i n_j d\mu, \quad (7)$$

where (k, l) and (i, j) go through the six combinations of indices. More details are given in [17].

Equation (7) implies that we need at least six radial velocity variances from different beam directions to compute the six Reynolds stresses. If the nacelle lidar has fewer than six beams, only σ_u^2 (R_{uu}) can be determined well and the stresses involving the lateral component will be more noisy [18]. For lidars that have fewer than six beams, we use another two ways to retrieve only σ_u^2 from the simulated measurements under different assumptions. The first is to correct all radial velocity variances $\sigma_{v_r}^2$ with a factor of $\cos^2 \phi$, which is the same as solving Eq. (4) assuming that all Reynolds stresses apart from σ_u^2 are zero (denoted as ‘ σ_u^2 -LSP’ method). The second is to assume that turbulence is isotropic, which gives σ_u^2 as the mean of all $\sigma_{v_r}^2$ (denoted as ‘ σ_u^2 -isotropy’ method).

3. Lidar scanning patterns

Figure 1 shows the considered lidar scanning patterns. The SpinnerLidar (SL in short) scans in a rosette-curve pattern and generates 400 radial velocities in one full scan. In practice, the SpinnerLidar streams out radial velocities at a rate of 200 Hz so it takes 2 s to finish one full scan. It has half-cone opening angles between $0-30^\circ$ and measures with a focus distance $f_d = 52$ m ($1D$) in front of the rotor. Other lidars have $\phi = 15^\circ$ and measure further away (at the focus distance of 98 m) to cover the whole rotor plane. Furthermore, we simulate all considered lidars with multiple measurement planes at $f_d = 49, 72, 98, 121$ and 142 m. We use the simulated radial velocity variances at all measurement levels to compute the turbulence statistics. Figure 2 illustrates the scanning trajectories of the 4-beam and 50-beam lidars with multiple planes as examples. To investigate the influences of the lidar opening angle and the focus distance on turbulence estimation, we simulate the 6-beam configuration [11] with a fixed focus distance of 52 m and increasing opening angles (Fig. 3(a)), and a fixed opening angle of 15° and increasing focus distances (Fig. 3(b)). We neglect the lidar probe volume and assume that the lidar can measure at a point in the simulation.

Figure 1: Scanning patterns of the simulated lidars. The SpinnerLidar (h) has $\phi = 0 - 30^\circ$ and scans at $f_d = 52$ m, while other lidars (a-g) have $\phi = 15^\circ$ and scan at $f_d = 98$ m to cover the whole rotor plane. Red dots represent the lidar beam scanning locations. The wind turbine rotor is indicated in a black circle.

4. Results

We compare the six Reynolds stresses computed from the simulated measurements of lidars, which have more than six beams and measure with a single plane, with those from a sonic anemometer at hub height, as shown in Fig. 4. The SpinnerLidar gives the best estimation for all six components, which is closely related to the maximum ϕ of the lidar. The 6-beam and 51-beam lidar provide very similar results, with larger errors and higher uncertainties than the SpinnerLidar. However, the 50-beam configuration cannot estimate the v - and w -variances accurately. This is because the least-squares problem can lead to infinite solutions if we have

Figure 2: Scanning trajectories of the 4-beam and the 50-beam lidars with multiple measurement planes at $f_d = 49, 72, 98, 121$ and 142 m. Red dots represent the lidar beam scanning locations. The wind turbine rotor is indicated in a black circle. The turbine nacelle is marked in a black dot on the rotor plane.

Figure 3: Scanning patterns of the 6-beam lidar with (a) a fixed focus distance and various half-cone opening angles, and (b) a fixed half-cone opening angle and various focus distances. The wind turbine rotor is indicated in a black circle. The turbine nacelle is marked in a black dot on the rotor plane.

only one ϕ value. Comparing the results from 50-beam and 51-beam lidar, we can see that adding one central beam is very beneficial for measuring all variances.

We show the performances of 50-beam and 51-beam lidar with multiple measurement planes on the Reynolds stresses estimation in Fig. 5, where the estimates using a single plane (marked in green and blue) are the same as those in Fig. 4. The comparison shows that if the measurements at a single plane are not sufficient to retrieve all Reynolds stresses, measuring at multiple planes with the same beam configuration does not help in the turbulence reconstruction. Results from the 51-beam lidar suggest that using multiple measurement planes does not improve the results much in our simulations; it only reduces slightly the uncertainty of the estimations.

Figure 6 shows the four Reynolds stresses retrieved from the 4-beam and 5-beam lidars assuming that the $\langle u'v' \rangle$ and $\langle v'w' \rangle$ covariances are negligible in Eq. (7). The Reynolds stress estimates are very noisy so that some of them are out of the limit of the axis. In all cases, the determinants of the matrix that results when expanding Eq. (7) are close to zero, which

Figure 4: Reynolds stresses derived from the virtual sonic anemometer and lidars, which have more than six beams and measure at a single distance, from 100 simulated wind fields. The markers are the means and the error bars are \pm one standard deviation.

Figure 5: Reynolds stresses derived from the virtual sonic anemometer, the 50-beam and 51-beam lidars measuring at a single plane and at multiple planes from 100 simulated wind fields. The markers are the means and the error bars are \pm one standard deviation.

indicates that the four Reynolds stresses cannot be estimated accurately using the least-square procedure with the 4-beam and 5-beam configurations. Again, the comparison suggests that using multiple measurement planes does not improve the results much in our simulations.

In Fig. 7, we analyze how the accuracy and the uncertainty of the Reynolds stresses estimation change when increasing ϕ and f_d of the 6-beam lidar. We compare them with those from the sonic anemometer and the SpinnerLidar. Both the error and the uncertainty decrease as the opening angle increases. Specifically, for $\phi = 45^\circ$, the six-beams configuration provides lower uncertainty than the SpinnerLidar despite having much fewer beams. Increasing the focus distance has an opposite effect as increasing the beams' opening angles due to the random error on the variances of the radial velocity. The radial velocity variances of the beams are less correlated when the lidar scans over a larger area. We performed the same analysis with the 51-beam lidar and observed the same trends (not shown here).

Figure 6: Reynolds stresses derived from the virtual sonic anemometer, the 4-beam and 5-beam lidars measuring at a single plane and at multiple planes from 100 simulated wind fields. The markers are the means and the error bars are \pm one standard deviation.

Figure 7: Influence of increasing opening angle ϕ and focus distance f_d on the Reynolds stresses estimation for the virtual sonic anemometer, the SpinnerLidar, and all 6-beam lidar configurations from 100 simulated wind fields.

We also simulate the nacelle lidars with all considered scanning patterns at the five measurement planes mentioned above, and retrieve the along-wind variance using the ‘ σ_u^2 -LSP’ and ‘ σ_u^2 -isotropy’ methods, respectively. The results are shown in Fig. 8. Table 1 summarizes the relative errors of the lidar-derived estimates compared to the one from the sonic anemometer. The results in first row are computed solving Eq. (7), from which we get perfect estimations of the along-wind variance using lidars with more than six beams. Furthermore, we find as an overall trend that lidar-derived σ_u^2 are overestimated using the ‘LSP’ method, when compared to the estimate from the sonic anemometer, while they are slightly underestimated using the ‘isotropy’ method. The biases are in general smaller when σ_u^2 are computed using the ‘isotropy’ method. Overall, all simulated lidars are able to estimate σ_u^2 well, despite of their different number of beams. The staring lidar acts like a sonic anemometer in our simulation and achieves zero relative error since no probe volume is considered and the beam is perfectly aligned with the along-wind component.

Figure 8: The along-wind variance derived from simulated lidars using the ‘ σ_u^2 -LSP’ method (in solid lines) and ‘ σ_u^2 -isotropy’ method (in dashed lines). All lidars measure at multiple planes.

Table 1: Relative error of the mean value of the lidar-derived along-wind variance using 100 simulated wind fields, when compared to the one from the sonic anemometer. All lidars measure at multiple planes. Negative values indicate that the along-wind variance is underestimated.

	staring	2-beam	4-beam	5-beam	6-beam	50-beam	51-beam	SL
$\langle u'u' \rangle$ [%]	—	—	—	—	0.00	—	0.00	0.17
σ_u^2 -LSP [%]	0	4.75	3.76	2.92	3.03	3.65	3.56	6.53
σ_u^2 -isotropy [%]	0	-2.27	-3.91	-2.52	-2.66	-3.30	-3.23	-6.07

5. Conclusion and Outlook

Our results show that at least six beams, including one beam with a different opening angle, are needed to estimate all the six Reynolds stresses accurately. The accuracy and uncertainty in turbulence characterization are better improved by enlarging the opening angle than by increasing the number of beams. Enlarging the measurement area of the nacelle lidars with the same beam orientation reduces the accuracy and increases the uncertainty. Compared to the point-wise sonic anemometer, all considered lidars can estimate the along-wind variance with

a relative error lower than 7%. All in all, the lidar with a 6-beam configuration and a large opening angle gives the best estimates of all Reynolds stresses.

This study should be extended by modelling the lidar probe volume in the simulation, which can cause turbulence attenuation. For continuous-wave lidar, the focus distance is closely related to the impact of the probe volume. Further studies on the lidar scanning pattern should also consider the inhomogeneity of the inflow. Modern wind turbines are often operating inside a wind farm or have large vertical span among the rotor area. Under those conditions, the turbulence homogeneity assumption is violated. Therefore, there is a need to investigate the scanning strategy for characterizing inhomogeneous inflows.

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